

Highly Dispersive Liquid Crystal Diffraction Gratings with Continuously Varying Periodicity

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Abstract

By using well-designed anchoring patterns in a liquid crystal (LC) device, novel electro-optic components with enhanced functionality can be designed. We present two types of nematic LC diffraction gratings with varying periodicity, manufactured with patterned photoalignment at the confining substrates. By varying the surface anchoring periodicity, the incident light can be redirected into many different diffraction orders, giving rise to a scattering appearance of the grating. In Type I gratings the anchoring patterns at the top and bottom substrates are aligned in the same direction, whereas in the Type II grating the anchoring patterns at the top and bottom substrates have a relative rotation of 90° . The structural and optical properties of the gratings can be tuned by applying an external voltage. The director configuration in the bulk is revealed with the use of polarizing optical microscopy images and numerical simulations. Experimental results of the diffraction spectra and intensities of different diffraction orders are supported by finite difference time domain (FDTD) simulations. The results specifically aim at tunable LC diffraction gratings which are highly dispersive and have weak zeroth order diffraction. In general, this work is a contribution to the field of LC flat optical components with electric tunability.

Keywords: liquid crystals, diffraction gratings, photoalignment, variable period, optics

1. Introduction

Optical elements based on liquid crystals (LCs) are widely used for different applications due to their mechanical and electro-optical properties. LCs can self-organize into complex configurations and possess orientational ordering which can be tuned via external stimuli such as an electric field. The average orientation direction of the rod-like molecular building blocks in the LC is described by the director. The emergent optical birefringence is actively exploited in LC based electro-optical devices. By enclosing LC material between substrates, it is possible to tune the director configuration in the enclosed LC material both via surface anchoring or via external stimuli such as electric fields. Tunable LC-based optical elements are in use for applications such as displays [1], filters [1, 2], lenses [3, 1, 4], sensors [1, 5], lasers [1, 6], smart windows [7, 8, 9, 10] and augmented reality glasses [11, 12].

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Many recently investigated LC diffraction gratings utilize the principle of the Pancharatnam-Berry (PB) phase or geometric phase to change the phase of the light passing through the LC optical element, whereas traditional optical elements rely on the difference in refractive index and geometry [13, 14]. Such LC diffraction gratings can be much thinner and have a higher efficiency than conventional gratings and can be used for applications such as beam shaping [15], beam steering [16, 17], beam combining [18], wave guiding [3] and in devices for augmented reality [19] and virtual reality [16].

LC optical devices with advanced optical functionality often rely on anchoring patterns at the substrates of the LC cell. Complex anchoring patterns can be created with various methods, such as micro-rubbing (for coarse alignment patterns) [20], lithography [21, 22], ion-beam etching [23], self-assembled monolayers [24], and photoalignment [25, 26]. Photoalignment is nowadays widely used as a strong technique to define complex anchoring patterns at the substrates with a variation in the planar anchoring direction [27, 28]. During the photoalignment process, there is no physical contact with the surface of the substrates, which reduces dust and charges on the surface, which are common for traditional rubbing processes. With photoalignment, it is possible to create alignment patterns with very short periods, especially when interference illumination is used. However, due to the high elastic energy related to small feature sizes and to avoid out-of-plane reorientation of the bulk director, 1D nematic LC diffraction gratings often have a period that is larger than the cell thickness [29, 27, 28, 14]. This typically limits the smallest period of (non-chiral) nematic LC diffraction gratings to an order of magnitude of several micrometer. Also smaller feature sizes have been reported and the limit imposed by the elastic energy can be overcome using chiral dopants and different manufacturing techniques [14, 30, 31].

In this work we demonstrate through experiments and computer simulations the design and optical behavior of two types of LC diffraction gratings with a variable surface periodicity. This in contrast to regularly studied gratings with a fixed periodicity. Both one-dimensional (Type I) and two-dimensional (Type II) gratings are fabricated and tested, including the electrical tunability. The diffraction gratings in this work can be manufactured with the help of commonly available photoalignment and LC materials, which makes them affordable. Variation of the surface anchoring parameters allows to realize a wide range of diffraction patterns, therefore the gratings can be adapted for specific applications. In general, this work aims at the field of LC flat optical components which are strongly dispersive and have easily accessible electric tunability.

2. Optical device design and methods

2.1. Grating design with photoalignment patterning

Using photoalignment patterning, we have designed two types of LC diffraction gratings, Type I and Type II. The diffraction gratings have a variable surface periodicity and both types differ by the orientation of the anchoring pattern on the top and the bottom substrate. In Type I gratings the anchoring patterns at the top and bottom substrates are aligned in the same direction, whereas in the Type II grating the anchoring patterns at the top and bottom substrates have a relative rotation of 90° . The Type II gratings are inspired by earlier experiments reported by Nys et al. for a fixed alignment period [27, 28, 32]. By using a variable surface anchoring period, the aim is to extend this concept and demonstrate efficient splitting of the diffraction orders. With the use of photoalignment, we define the planar director anchoring as:

$$\phi(x) = \frac{\pi x}{P} + \alpha \beta \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{\beta P}\right) + \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (1)$$

where $\phi(x)$ is the azimuthal angle of the alignment with respect to the x axis, P is the base period, α is the period variation parameter, and β is the superperiod parameter. The variation parameter α is limited to values between 0 and 1 and the superperiod parameter β is a positive integer. The anchoring parameters α , β will affect the splitting of the diffraction orders into sub-orders and their diffraction efficiency, which will be further investigated. A π rotation of the azimuthal anchoring angle results in the same alignment direction, explaining why P is called the base period (corresponding to $\alpha = 0$). The superperiod of the alignment pattern can be identified as $2\beta P$, and the director rotates over an angle $2\beta \cdot \pi$ within this superperiod (Figure 1). To vary the surface anchoring pattern as described in Eq.1, in this work a SLM-based illumination setup is used (see section 2.2), limiting the minimal feature size and therefore imposing experimental constraints on $(1 - \alpha) \cdot P$ (and accordingly the maximal diffraction angle).

The director configuration in the bulk of the LC cell is dependent on the anchoring pattern, the thickness of the cell, the voltage applied across the cell, and the LC material parameters. By tuning the voltage across the cell it is possible to tune the power in the different diffraction orders [27, 28].

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the surface anchoring patterns in Type I (a) and Type II (b) cells. The anchoring pattern (described by $\phi(x)$, Eq. 1) is illustrated in (c) for three different (α, β) combinations.

2.2. Sample preparation

To produce the LC cell, glass substrates with an indium tin oxide (ITO) electrode layer were covered with a photoalignment layer in the cleanroom facilities at Ghent University. Photoalignment illumination was performed with the help of an optical setup making use of a blue laser (Cobolt Twist, 200 mW, $\lambda = 457$ nm) and a spatial light modulator (SLM). The SLM (Holoeye Pluto 2) has a resolution of 1920 by 1080 pixels and a pixel pitch of $8 \mu\text{m}$. The gray-scale pattern that is displayed on the SLM defines the polarization pattern that is projected on the substrate, as

described in more detail in previous articles [33, 34]. By adjusting the gray-scale pattern that is displayed on the SLM, a variety of surface anchoring patterns (with different values for the alignment parameters α and β (Eq. 1)) can be written on demand. Planar LC anchoring is obtained with a preferred azimuthal orientation perpendicular to the linear polarization of the laser illumination. For the photoalignment material, a solution of Brilliant Yellow (BY, Sigma-Aldrich, 0.2 wt%) in dimethylformamide (Sigma-Aldrich) is used. Cleaned glass substrates are treated with an ozone plasma to improve the quality of the coating and the photoalignment layer is spincoated (3000 rpm, 30s) on the ITO-covered side of the substrates. After spincoating, the substrates are dried on a hotplate for 5 min at 90°C. The periodically rotating azimuthal alignment pattern is defined at both substrates with the help of the blue laser setup with the SLM. For the Type I cell, the cell is assembled before photoalignment illumination. For the Type II cells, the two substrates are illuminated separately and after photoalignment, they are assembled in a cell, so that there is a 90° rotation between the alignment patterns at the top and bottom substrates (see Figure 1). The anchoring patterns at both substrates are one-dimensional, so precision alignment of both substrates is not necessary. Different alignment configurations are tested: $\alpha = (0.2, 0.4, 0.6)$; $\beta = (2, 3, 4)$; $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$. The substrates are glued together with a glue (NOA 68) that contains spherical spacers (3 μm diameter in the Type I cell and 5.5 μm diameter in the Type II cell). For Type I cells, the glue is cured before photoalignment illumination, while this is done after photoalignment in Type II cells. Glue is only present at the edges of the cell and only these regions are illuminated to polymerize the glue, while the photoaligned area of the cell is covered with aluminum foil. After gluing, the cell is filled with nematic LC E7 at 80°C before cooling down to room temperature. All the experiments have been performed at room temperature ($\approx 21^\circ\text{C}$).

2.3. Experimental setup

In order to verify the alignment of the LC, we perform polarization microscopy analysis with a Nikon Eclipse LV100POL microscope. The cell is placed in between crossed polarizers and during the analysis, we apply different voltages across the cells, ranging from 0 V_{rms} to 3 V_{rms} (1 kHz frequency). With such a voltage sweep we verify that the LC in the cell is properly aligned and that it contains few defects.

Each of the LC diffraction grating samples is placed on a mount in the path of a helium-neon laser beam $\lambda = 633 \text{ nm}$ (JDS Uniphase) with diameter approximately 1 mm. The laser is linearly polarized, but by using a $\lambda/4$ plate in front of the cell, the incident beam becomes right handed circularly polarized (RCP). Each LC grating sample is illuminated individually and the resulting diffraction pattern is recorded on a black screen behind the sample with the help of a cellphone camera (Figure 2). No precautions have been taken to avoid saturation of the camera when capturing the diffraction images, so they cannot be used to quantitatively analyze the diffraction efficiencies. To measure the diffraction efficiency in the different diffraction orders for the Type I gratings, a photodetector (Newport 918D - SL - 0D3R) was attached to the power meter (Newport 2936-C) and the measured power in each diffraction order was divided by the total power incident in front of the sample. We use the same experimental setup for Type I and Type II LC diffraction grating samples but in Type II gratings the diffraction efficiency in all the different orders is not explicitly measured. The diffraction patterns are recorded for different applied voltages, ranging from 0 V_{rms} to 3 V_{rms} (1 kHz frequency).

2.4. Simulation methods

For Type I and Type II gratings we applied a different methodology in order to calculate the diffraction patterns in relation to different anchoring parameters, the cell thickness and the

Figure 2: Setup for the diffraction experiment, showing the incoming laser beam with wavevector k and right-hand circular polarization (RCP), and the LC cell across which voltage is applied. The diffraction pattern is observed on a black screen.

voltage across the cell. Type I diffraction gratings are periodic in only one direction, therefore the diffraction pattern also changes in only one direction. We estimate the diffraction pattern, by assuming that the director follows the alignment at the surface, independently of the z -coordinate. This is approximately valid as long as the surface anchoring period remains large compared to the cell thickness [30, 32]. The diffraction pattern can be calculated with an analytical method introduced by Escuti et al. [35], adjusted to the phase profile of our alignment configuration, as discussed in section 2.4.2. The director configuration at the substrates, the LC layer thickness d , the ordinary n_o and extraordinary n_e refractive indices of the material, and the Jones vector of the incoming light are the inputs of the method, and the output is the diffraction pattern.

The calculations of the diffraction pattern for the Type II gratings are more complex, since the anchoring at the top and bottom substrates are periodic in perpendicular directions, and the director configuration in the bulk of the cells is non-trivial, even for relatively thin cells. Therefore we must simulate a three-dimensional system. The nematic profile is calculated using Q-tensor simulations based on a custom build Finite-Element (FE) method (see Section 2.4.1). In parallel, using a Python Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) library Meep [36], a custom script is created to simulate the near-field of the diffracted light for a given dielectric tensor field (obtained from the Q-tensor simulations) inside one unit cell of the diffraction grating. Once the near field of the transmitted light is calculated, a Fast-Fourier Transform (FFT) is used to calculate the far-field diffraction pattern.

2.4.1. Q-tensor simulations for Type II gratings

To simulate the LC director configuration in the bulk of the type II gratings for different applied voltages, a finite element Q-tensor simulation method is used [37, 27, 28, 38]. The Q-tensor is used as an order tensor to describe the LC and the director distribution, and is found by minimizing the Landau-de Gennes free energy functional. The alignment conditions at the top and bottom interfaces are included using strong anchoring conditions and the pretilt is set to zero.

The azimuthal anchoring angle varies as $\phi(x) = \frac{\pi x}{P} + \alpha\beta \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{\beta P}\right) + \pi/2$ on the bottom substrate and $\phi(y) = \frac{\pi y}{P} + \alpha\beta \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{\beta P}\right) + \pi/2$ on the top substrate. The unit cell considered in the simulations has dimension $(2\beta) \cdot P$ in both the x- and y-direction and periodic boundary conditions are used in these directions (Figure 3). The cell thickness $d = 5.5 \mu\text{m}$ (corresponding to the experimentally used spacer diameter) is taken into account in the simulations and voltages are applied between the uniform electrodes at the top and bottom substrates. Contributions from the elastic energy, electric energy and thermotropic (bulk) energy are taken into account in the Landau-de Gennes free energy functional. The electrostatic field is determined from the variational form of Laplace's equation. The elastic and electric properties of the LC material E7 are taken into account in the simulations and the bulk thermotropic coefficients are based on the ones measured for 5CB at a reduced temperature of -2°C ($K_{11} = 11.1 \text{ pN}$, $K_{22} = 6.5 \text{ pN}$, $K_{33} = 17.1 \text{ pN}$, $\varepsilon_{\perp} = 5.2$, $\varepsilon_{\parallel} = 19.0$), giving rise to an equilibrium order parameter of 0.54. This simulation approach has been shown to accurately reproduce the experimental results in previous works with fixed alignment period P [27, 28].

Figure 3: Optical axis structure of designed diffraction gratings, represented as the azimuthal angle ϕ (w.r.t. the x-axis) and polar angle θ_p (w.r.t. the xy-plane) of the director configurations for Type I (a) and Type II (b)-(c) cells with anchoring parameters $\alpha = 0.4$ and $\beta = 2$. (a) Also shows the coordinate axes of the system and the direction of the incident (wavevector k), and diffracted light. (c) Shows the mid-plane director configuration at $z = d/2$ (marked with black) in the Type II cell from (b).

2.4.2. Diffraction pattern simulations

The diffraction pattern of Type I diffraction gratings is calculated with a method based on Escuti et al. [35]. The first step of the method is to calculate the near-field as a Jones vector E_{out} , which is given by $\mathbf{E}_{out} = \underline{T}(x) \cdot \mathbf{E}_{in}$. The transfer matrix $\underline{T}(x)$ is given as:

$$\underline{T}(x) = \underline{R}(\phi(x)) \begin{bmatrix} \exp\left(-\frac{i2\pi n_e d}{\lambda}\right) & 0 \\ 0 & \exp\left(-\frac{i2\pi n_o d}{\lambda}\right) \end{bmatrix} \underline{R}^T(\phi(x)), \quad (2)$$

where the $\underline{R}(\phi(x))$ is the rotation matrix, $\phi(x)$ is the azimuthal angle of the director alignment at the substrates (see Eq. 1 and figure 4 (a)), n_o and n_e are the material specific ordinary and extraordinary refractive indices and λ is the wavelength of light.

The vector corresponding to the far field \mathbf{D}_m is calculated as a Fourier transform of \mathbf{E}_{out} :

$$\mathbf{D}_m = \frac{1}{2\beta P} \int_0^{2\beta P} \mathbf{E}_{\text{out}} \cdot e^{-im \cdot x/\beta P} dx, \quad (3)$$

where β and P are the anchoring parameters as defined in Eq.1. We numerically calculate the integral \mathbf{D}_m for values of $m \in (-30, 30)$ in order to obtain the diffraction pattern.

Figure 4: Structure (a) and the simulated diffraction efficiency (b),(c) of Type I diffraction gratings. (a) shows the azimuthal angle of the anchoring at the substrates for $\alpha = 0.2, 0.4$ and $\beta = 2, 4$. (b) shows the diffraction efficiency of Type I diffraction gratings with anchoring parameters from (a). (c) shows the value of M_2 measure for Type I diffraction gratings with anchoring parameters $\alpha = 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5$ and $\beta = 2, 4, 6, 8$. (d) shows the diffraction efficiency of the Type I diffraction gratings ($\alpha = 0.4, \beta = 4.0$) with respect to Δn . In all simulations the thickness is $d = 3 \mu\text{m}$ and $\Delta n = 0.12$, except (d).

The diffraction angle θ is related to the value of m via $\theta = \arcsin\left(m \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2\beta P}\right)$. The non-zero diffraction orders are centered around $\theta_c = \arcsin(\lambda/P)$, which corresponds to the angle of the first diffraction order for diffraction gratings with a fixed period P . The first central order associated with the base period P , actually corresponds to a value $m = 2\beta$ for the diffraction order in the analytical definition based on Eq. 3.

The far-field diffraction pattern of Type II gratings is calculated by using FFT of the near-field transmission obtained via the FDTD method (custom build script using Meep library). Key parameters for the near-field simulations are the dielectric tensor field, which is calculated directly from the simulated Q-tensor field (see Section 2.4.1). The imported dielectric tensor field is locally interpolated in order to fit the voxel grid of the FDTD simulation. We set the grid density equal to 20 points per μm . The direction, wavelength and polarization of the incoming light are specified in the simulations so that they match the values in the experiments.

3. Experimental results

3.1. Type I diffraction gratings

The experimental results for the Type I cells, with a 1D periodic variation along the x-axis at the top and bottom substrate (Figure 1), are summarized in Figure 5. Gratings with different $\alpha = (0.2, 0.4)$, $\beta = (2, 4)$ combinations are produced, with base period $P = 10 \mu m$. POM images between crossed polarizers are shown in Figure 5(a) together with the captured diffraction patterns (at $1.5 V_{rms}$). The measured diffraction efficiencies (at $1.5 V_{rms}$) for the different orders are summarized in Figure 5(b). The diffraction spot corresponding to first order diffraction associated with the base period $P = 10 \mu m$ is indicated in the diffraction images by a white arrow and by a black vertical line in the plot with measured diffraction efficiencies (Figure 5(b)). The first order diffraction angle associated with $P = 10 \mu m$ is equal to $\theta = \arcsin\left(\frac{\lambda}{P}\right) = 3.63^\circ$. The cell thickness for the 1D gratings was $3 \mu m$, roughly corresponding to a full wave thickness for the 633 nm Helium-neon laser, giving rise to a strong zeroth order transmission in the absence of an applied voltage. To obtain efficient diffraction (different from the zeroth order transmission), a voltage of $1.5 V_{rms}$ was applied to the cell. The diffraction images and diffraction efficiencies in Figure 5 are captured in these conditions ($1.5 V_{rms}$ applied, 1 kHz frequency). This allows us to easily observe the effect of variations in the anchoring parameters α, β on the diffraction pattern.

For a 1D grating with fixed period $P = 10 \mu m$ ($\alpha = 0$ in Eq.1), apart from the zeroth order transmission only one diffraction order (first order) appears for circularly polarized incident light [35]. It is clear that a variable surface anchoring period (non-zero α in Eq.1) results in an increased number of diffraction orders, with sub-orders appearing at symmetric positions with respect to the central first order (associated with the base period P). Increasing α leads to the appearance of more (non-negligible) diffraction orders, giving rise to redistribution of light over a larger angular range. Increasing β on the other hand gives rise to the appearance of more diffraction orders, but with a smaller angular separation between different sub-orders.

3.2. Type II diffraction gratings

The experimental results for the Type II cells, with a 1D periodic variation along the x-axis at the bottom substrate and along the y-axis at the top substrate (Figure 1), are summarized in Figure 6. Gratings with different $\alpha = (0.2, 0.4, 0.6)$, $\beta = (2, 3, 4)$ combinations are produced, with base period $P = 10 \mu m$. The alignment patterns at the top and bottom substrate are always constructed with the same α, β, P parameters, but they are oriented in perpendicular directions. The measured cell thickness for the Type II gratings was approximately $6 \mu m$. POM images (at $0 V_{rms}$, $1.5 V_{rms}$ and $3 V_{rms}$) between crossed polarizers are shown together with captured diffraction patterns at $0 V_{rms}$, $1.5 V_{rms}$ and $3 V_{rms}$. This allows us to evaluate the electrical tunability and observe the effect of variations in the anchoring parameters α, β on the diffraction pattern. In the POM images, an area of $6\beta \cdot P$ by $6\beta \cdot P$ is shown, corresponding to 3 by 3 unit cells. Although some defect lines are

Figure 5: Experimentally captured POM images between crossed polarizers and diffraction patterns (a) together with measured efficiencies into different diffraction orders (b) for type I gratings. The images of the diffraction pattern (a) do not allow for quantitative analysis of the diffraction efficiency (due to saturation of the camera). Results are shown for alignment patterns with three different (α, β) combinations equal to (0.2, 4), (0.4, 4) and (0.4, 2). The cell thickness is $3 \mu\text{m}$ and the base period P is $10 \mu\text{m}$. Diffraction images and measurements are shown for an applied voltage of $1.5 V_{rms}$. The central first diffraction order associated with the base period $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding to a diffraction angle $\theta = \arcsin\left(\frac{\lambda}{P}\right) = 3.63^\circ$, is indicated by a white arrow in (a) and a vertical black line in (b).

visible in Figure 6(c), in general reasonably large areas with a defect-free director configuration can be observed. In this way proper diffraction patterns can be obtained corresponding to earlier observations for cell with a fixed alignment period P [27, 28].

Figures 6(a)-(c) demonstrate the effect of variable $\beta = (2, 3, 4)$ for fixed $\alpha = 0.2$, while results for increased values of α are shown in Figure 6 (d)-(e) (with respectively $(\alpha, \beta) = (0.4, 2)$ and $(0.6, 4)$). In general, regarding the effect of alignment parameters α and β , similar observations hold as for the Type I gratings: larger values of α give rise to a distribution of light over a larger angular range, while larger values of β give rise to a distribution over more sub-orders with smaller angular separation.

Regarding the electrical tunability, it is clear that the diffraction pattern can be easily reconfigured with the help of relatively small electric fields ($< 1 V_{rms} / \mu\text{m}$). At higher voltages ($3 V_{rms}$), the light is mainly transmitted into the zeroth order and only weak scattering in some diffraction orders along k_x and k_y is observed. Similar to what is observed in the Type I gratings, the central diffraction order along k_x and k_y is associated with a spatial period $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$, corresponding with a diffraction angle $\theta = \arcsin\left(\frac{\lambda}{P}\right) = 3.63^\circ$. At $0 V_{rms}$ the light is distributed into many diffraction orders. In most cases light is mainly distributed in the bottom-left and bottom-right quadrant, centered around the diagonal diffraction points associated with spatial periodicity $\sqrt{2} \cdot P$ along the diagonal, corresponding with a diffraction angle $\theta = \arcsin\left(\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2} \cdot P}\right)$. Also at $1.5 V_{rms}$ a strong redistribution of light by the 2D gratings is observed, resulting in multiple clearly visible diffrac-

Figure 6: Experimentally captured POM images (0V) between crossed polarizers and diffraction patterns (0V, 1.5V and 3V) for type II gratings. Results are shown for alignment patterns with five different (α, β) combinations equal to (0.2, 4), (0.2, 3), (0.2, 4), (0.4, 2) and (0.6, 4) from left to right (a)-(e). The cell thickness is $6 \mu\text{m}$ and the base period P is $10 \mu\text{m}$. Diffraction images are captured for three different applied voltages 0V, 1.5V and 3V from top to bottom. Four important diffraction orders, corresponding to the central 1st diffraction order associated with a base period $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$ along k_x and k_y , and to the central diffraction orders associated with period $\sqrt{2} \cdot P$ and $\sqrt{2}/2 \cdot P$ along the diagonal, are indicated by white circles in the diffraction images captures at $1.5 V_{rms}$.

tion orders, especially situated along k_x and k_y as well as in the bottom-right (fourth) quadrant of the (k_x, k_y) diagram. A group of diffraction orders is centered around the diagonal diffraction point associated with spatial periodicity $\sqrt{2} \cdot P$ and the second group of points is centered around the diffraction order corresponding to a spatial periodicity $\sqrt{2}/2 \cdot P$ along the diagonal. For clarity, these points are indicated by white circles in the diffraction images captured at $1.5 V_{rms}$ (Figure 6) together with the central first diffraction orders along k_x and k_y .

4. Simulation results

4.1. Type I diffraction gratings

The simulation results for Type I gratings are summarized in Figure 4. Results are shown for different α and β combinations and for different values of the birefringence. The used values for

n_o and n_e are based on the characteristic values for E7, but n_e is replaced by a voltage dependent n_{eff} to take into account the out-of-plane tilt of the director introduced by an applied voltage. Specifically, to approximately simulate the diffraction patterns in Figure 4(b), we reduced the birefringence to 0.12 in the analytical model for Type I cells, without changing the director configuration. The estimated value of 0.12 for the birefringence (used in Figure 4(b) and (c)) corresponds to the experimental condition in which a voltage of $1.5 V_{rms}$ is applied to the cell. Additional simulation results for different values of the birefringence are shown in Figure 4(d), to show the effect on the diffraction efficiency. A more accurate -but much more methodologically advanced- approach is to use full diffraction modelling, as we show for Type II gratings.

In agreement with experiments, the first central diffraction order is split into many sub-orders when a variable surface anchoring period is present. The total angular separation of the non-negligible diffraction orders increases with parameter α , giving rise to redistribution of light over a larger angular range (Figure 4(b)). The number of sub-orders increases with β , but the angular separation between different sub-orders decreases (Figure 4(b)). The α parameter determines the total angular spreading and β parameter determines the granularity of the first central order (associated with base period P). In order to better quantize the effects of the anchoring parameters, we introduce a scalar measure M_2 as:

$$M_2^2 = \frac{1}{\sum_{n=0}^N I_n} \sum_{n=0}^N (\theta_n - \theta_c)^2 I_n, \quad (4)$$

which represents the angular standard deviation of the diffraction pattern around the angle of the first central order. M_2 is a good measure of the angular spreading of the first central order, as can be seen in Figure 4(c). Adjusting the value β has no effect on M_2 , while M_2 clearly increases for increasing values of α .

4.2. Type II diffraction gratings

The simulation results for the diffraction pattern in Type II gratings are summarized in Figure 7 and 8. Figure 7 shows the diffraction patterns for different values of alignment parameters α , β and P , whereas Figure 8 the role of variation in LC layer thickness and the applied voltage. Results show that the angles/k-vectors in the diffraction pattern are well responsive to the parameters α , β and P (Figure 7). Different clusters of diffraction points can be identified, consisting of a central diffraction point and multiple suborders spread around this central point. A few of these central diffraction points can be identified, along k_x , along k_y or along the (k_x, k_y) diagonal or anti-diagonal, as indicated in Figure 7. Central diffraction orders along the diagonal are found by the relation $\theta_c = \arcsin(\lambda/(\sqrt{2}/2P))$ and $\theta_c = \arcsin(\lambda/(\sqrt{2}P))$ (see Figure 7(a), 7(c)).

Figure 8(a) shows the scattered light in different quadrants of the diffraction images as the thickness of the cell increases and the intensity of the diffraction orders and their sub-orders also decreases. The former can be mostly explained with polarization conversion mechanisms (see Section 4.2) and the latter is due to the fact the more light is scattered into other diffraction orders. Figure 8(b) shows that the thickness of the cell has an (almost periodic) effect on the diffraction efficiency of the zeroth order, but the zeroth order efficiency remains low (below 10 percent for cells with a thickness between 3 and $6.5 \mu m$) at $0 V_{rms}$. This result is different from Type I gratings (section 5.1). The voltage applied across the cell has a strong effect on the diffraction efficiency of the zeroth order (see Figure 8(d)). There is a minimum of diffraction efficiency of the zeroth order at $1.2 V_{rms}$. The effects of the thickness of the cell and the applied voltage are complementary, since both affect the director configuration and the experienced retardation in the

Figure 7: Simulated normalized intensity per unit area patterns of Type II diffraction gratings. (a) shows the diffraction patterns of cells with values $P = 5.0, 10.0, 15.0 \mu\text{m}$, $\beta = 2$, $\alpha = 0.4$ and $U = 0 V_{rms}$. (b) Shows diffraction patterns of cells with $\beta = 2.0, 3.0, 4.0$, $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$, $\alpha = 0.4$ and $U = 0 V_{rms}$. (c) Shows diffraction patterns of cells with $\alpha = 0.2, 0.4$, $\beta = 2.0, 3.0$, $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$ and $U = 0 V_{rms}$. On plots (a)-(c) white circles mark four important diffraction orders: central 1st diffraction order associated with a base period $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$ along k_x and k_y , and the central diffraction orders associated with period $\sqrt{2} \cdot P$ and $2\sqrt{2} \cdot P$ along the diagonal.

bulk of the diffraction gratings. As the thickness of the cell increases the out-of-plane orientation in the bulk of the layer becomes more pronounced [27, 28], and the director also increasingly aligns with the external field as the voltage increases.

5. Discussion

By comparing the experimental results (Figure 5 and 6) with numerical simulations (Figure 4, 7 and 8), in general a good agreement can be observed. We will focus on some specific aspects of the diffraction properties for Type I and Type II gratings.

5.1. Type I diffraction gratings

Both experimental results (Figure 5) and numerical simulations (Figure 4) demonstrate the effect of variations in the surface anchoring pattern defined by Eq.1. Introducing a variable alignment period, by using non-zero values of α , results in splitting of the diffraction orders, with new sub-orders appearing symmetrically around the (central) first diffraction order that is associated with the base period P . Larger values of α extend the angular range over which light is redistributed by the grating (increased M_2 in Figure 4(c)). The value of β does not influence the total

Figure 8: Simulated normalized intensity patterns per unit area and plots of diffraction efficiency in the zeroth order for the Type II diffraction gratings. (a) Diffraction patterns for different thicknesses of the cell, for cells with $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$, $\beta = 2$, $\alpha = 0.4$ and $U = 0 V_{rms}$. (b) Diffraction patterns for different voltages across the cell for cells with $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$, $\beta = 2$, $\alpha = 0.4$ and $d = 6.2 \mu\text{m}$. White circles mark four important diffraction orders: the central 1st diffraction order associated with a base period $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$ along k_x and k_y , and the central diffraction orders associated with period $\sqrt{2} \cdot P$ and $2\sqrt{2} \cdot P$ along the diagonal. (c) Diffraction efficiency of the zeroth order with respect to the thickness of the cell, for the same cells as in (a). (d) Diffraction efficiency of the zeroth order with respect to the voltage applied across the thickness of the cell, for cells with $P = 10 \mu\text{m}$, $\beta = 2$, $\alpha = 0.4$ and $d = 6.2 \mu\text{m}$.

angular spreading of the diffracted light, but affects the splitting into multiple sub-orders: larger β values give rise to increased granularity, with multiple (closely spaced) sub-orders appearing in the diffraction pattern. These effects are clearly demonstrated experimentally and confirmed by the theoretical prediction. Theory and experiments also show good quantitative correspondence for the relative ratios between different diffraction orders (see Figure 5 and Figure 4). This clearly confirms that the effects of the alignment parameters α , β are successfully taken into account by adjusting the theory as described in section 2.4.2.

Apart from the alignment parameters α , β and P , the cell thickness and applied voltage can be used to tune the diffraction behaviour. In Type I gratings, their effect on the diffraction pattern can be qualitatively understood from the theoretical framework for 1D polarization gratings with a fixed alignment period P [35]. In this approach, it is assumed that the LC director in the bulk perfectly follows the surface alignment at the interfaces. In the paraxial approximation, the diffraction efficiency can be written as $\eta_m = |\mathbf{D}_m|^2 / |\mathbf{E}_{in}|^2$ (see Eq. 3) where $|\mathbf{E}_{in}|^2$ is the intensity of the incident light, η_m and $|\mathbf{D}_m|^2$ are the diffraction efficiency and the diffraction intensity of the m -th order, respectively. The diffraction efficiencies can be expressed as $\eta_0 = \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi \Delta n d}{\lambda}\right)$ and

$\eta_{\pm 1} = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 \mp S'_3 \right] \sin^2 \left(\frac{\pi \Delta n d}{\lambda} \right)$, where λ is the wavelength of the incident light, and $S'_3 = S_3/S_0$ is the normalized Stokes parameter corresponding to the ellipticity of incident light. Only three diffraction orders (-1,0,1) are present for linearly polarized light and two orders appear for circularly polarized light ((-1,0) or (0,1) depending on the handedness). When the half wave condition is met ($\Delta n \cdot d = \lambda/2$), all the light is redirected towards the first order and no light is transmitted in the zeroth order. For smaller values of the retardation (below the half wave condition), the light is increasingly diffracted into the zeroth order, as confirmed by the simulations in Figure 4(d). These observations are also valid for 1D gratings with a variable alignment period as defined in Eq. 1, with the difference that the first order is split into multiple sub-orders.

To approximate this condition and experimentally meet the half wave condition, a voltage of $1.5 V_{rms}$ was applied to the cell. Accordingly, in the simulations (Figure 4(b)), the Δn is reduced to 0.12 (the value measured for E7 at $1.5 V_{rms}$). In the $3 \mu m$ thick cell with E7, at $1.5 V_{rms}$ the half wave condition is met for red light, which agrees with the experimental observation that the zeroth order diffraction is minimized at this voltage. However, as can be seen in Figure 5, approximately 20 percent of the light is still transmitted into the zeroth order. This can be understood by taking into account deviations from the ideal theory. In practice, the LC director in the bulk is known to somewhat deviate from the anchoring pattern at the surface and the paraxial approximation is only valid as a first approximation. Moreover, applying a voltage to the cell in order to meet the half wave condition is not equivalent to decreasing the cell thickness (although both give rise to a decreased retardation). The simplified theory can still be used to roughly understand the experimental behavior.

5.2. Type II diffraction gratings

In Type II gratings, the planar anchoring patterns at the top and bottom substrate cannot accommodate a bulk director configuration with only planar director orientation (parallel to the substrates) without the need for twist disclination lines. To avoid these twist conflicts imposed by the surface anchoring conditions, the director locally tilts out-of-plane, forming line-like regions with a homeotropic director orientation (perpendicular to the substrates) [27, 28, 32]. The regions with close to vertical director orientation form (slightly curved) lines roughly in the mid-plane of the cell, running approximately along the xy-diagonal (Figure 3). The spacing between these lines is related to the local alignment period in the surface anchoring pattern and is on average equal to $\sqrt{2} \cdot P$. Within a $2\beta \cdot P$ by $2\beta \cdot P$ unit cell, 2β lines with close to vertical midplane director appear, separated by lines along which the director is approximately planar orientated following the (diagonally) rotating surface anchoring pattern. This is well seen in Figure 3. The periodicity that appears along the xy-diagonal, gives rise to diagonal diffraction orders (centered around angles $\theta = \arcsin \left(\frac{\lambda}{P \cdot \sqrt{2}} \right)$ and $\theta = \arcsin \left(\frac{\lambda}{P \cdot \sqrt{2}/2} \right)$) as observed experimentally and by simulations (Figure 6 and Figure 7 and 8). The exact redistribution of light however strongly depends on the exact retardation that is experienced (depending on layer thickness and applied voltage) and on the alignment parameters α and β .

In Figure 8(a) it can be observed that the diffraction order with the highest intensity switches quadrants as the thickness of the cell increases. A similar effect is observed both experimentally (Figure 5) and in simulations (Figure 8b) for different applied voltages ($0 V_{rms}$ vs. $1.5 V_{rms}$) or layer thicknesses. This result is related to the variation in retardation and therefore polarization conversion that occurs inside the LC layer. In general, it is clear that the exact redistribution of light strongly depends on the exact retardation (related to layer thickness and applied voltage) that is experienced. This might as well explain why the diffraction pattern at $0 V_{rms}$ in Figure 6 (b)

for $(\alpha, \beta) = (0.2, 3)$ shows limited diffraction in the bottom-right quadrant, while the other (α, β) combinations show substantial diffraction in this quadrant as well at $0 V_{rms}$. The experimentally measured spacing between the glass substrates in the Type II grating varied around $6 \mu m$, with a slight inhomogeneity in the cell. Apart from the intended variation in (α, β) , it is clear that inhomogeneity in thickness can somewhat affect the exact diffraction pattern that is observed at a specific voltage. The high sensitivity of the diffraction properties to exact thickness and director profile limits the full quantitative agreement between experiments and simulations.

From $0 V_{rms}$ to $1.5 V_{rms}$ mainly a redistribution of light intensity between the bottom-left and bottom-right quadrant takes place (shifting more towards the bottom-right quadrant at $1.5 V_{rms}$) and the zeroth order diffraction is somewhat diminished. At higher voltages (e.g. $3 V_{rms}$), the LC molecules increasingly align with the electric field, which enhances the diffraction efficiency of the zeroth order (transmission). The 1D gratings associated with the top and bottom substrate become decoupled by a region with vertical director orientation [27]. Apart from the zeroth order transmission, only some weak diffraction into the k_x and k_y directions is observed (related to the 1D gratings at the top and bottom with a small retardation remaining at high voltages). This is clearly seen both experimentally (Figure 5) and in simulations (Figure 8). The interplay of the effects of the voltage and thickness, allows us to create diffraction gratings for which we can have a highly dispersive mode of operation and a transparent mode of operation, depending on the applied voltage. Redistribution of light into different quadrants can be achieved as well.

As in Type I gratings, the alignment parameters α , β and P also strongly influence the diffraction behaviour in Type II gratings. Larger values of α give rise to redistribution of light over a larger angular range and larger values of β give rise to an increased number of sub-orders with smaller angular separation (increased granularity). These general trends can be well observed both in experiments and simulations. In the Type II gratings, diffraction orders that are situated along the diagonal are split into two dimensions (both along k_x and k_y). Although the suborders are positioned symmetrically around the central order (associated with $\alpha=0$), the diffraction efficiency in symmetric positions is not necessarily equal. This is different from what is expected in Type I gratings (Figure 4) and is to some extent related to the overlap of diffraction spots. For larger values of α the diffraction orders start to overlap and it becomes unclear to which so-called cluster of diffraction spots different orders belong. The result is a highly scattered diffraction pattern with light distributed into many orders.

In Figure 6 it can be noted that sub-orders in the diffraction pattern centered around the diagonal points associated with periodicity $\sqrt{2}P$ are not always well separated from each other. Sometimes one extended zone with increased intensity is observed instead. This is especially the case for Figure 6(c) with $(\alpha, \beta) = (0.2, 4)$ and is a direct consequence of the fact that α is small while β is relatively large (giving rise to closely spaced sub-orders). In the experiments, the laser beams covers a relatively large area, which may contain disclination lines as well (see e.g. the POM image in Figure 6(c)). Domains at opposite sides of the disclination line, yield diffraction contributions with a different phase and as a result the narrow diffraction orders that are predicted by the simulations are blurred in the experimental results, in particular for the diffraction orders with central order around periodicity $\sqrt{2}P$ (and accordingly a small diffraction angle).

Finally, note that in this work we only use integer values for the parameter β because this yields a superperiod in the realized structures. If a non-rational real number is used for β , then the structure becomes non-periodic and the discrete diffraction orders could be smeared out over a continuum. This approach may be an interesting alternative for certain applications, if a higher degree of spreading of the light intensity is desired.

6. Conclusions

In this work we present two types of highly dispersive LC diffraction gratings with continuously varying periodicity, which have been manufactured using a photoalignment method. In Type I liquid crystal diffraction gratings the photoalignment patterns on the top and bottom substrate are periodic in the same direction, while in Type II variants the photoalignment patterns on the top and bottom substrate are rotated by 90° relative to each other. The director configuration in the bulk of the samples was verified with POM images and simulated by using the FE Q-tensor method. The diffraction patterns of the Type I samples were simulated using a Jones calculus method, and the diffraction patterns of the Type II diffraction gratings were numerically calculated using a FDTD method in combination with the FE Q-tensor simulations. Key results of the simulations were experimentally verified and vice versa. Splitting of the diffraction pattern into multiple sub-orders is investigated and the effect of the surface alignment parameters α and β (based on Eq.1) on the angular spreading of the diffraction spots and the granularity of the pattern is discussed.

Through the design of the anchoring pattern and by tuning the voltage applied across the grating, the diffraction efficiency into different diffraction orders can be tuned. This allows us to achieve a strongly scattering state where the LC diffraction grating has a low diffraction efficiency in the zeroth order and the light is spread efficiently into many other (off-axis) diffraction orders, and a state that is mainly transparent (strong zeroth order). By tuning the surface anchoring pattern, the angle of the central first diffraction order and the splitting into sub-orders can be tuned, in order to optimize the properties of the scattering state as envisioned. Consequently, these kinds of LC diffraction gratings could find applications as well in smart windows.

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